

The Issue of Charlatanin Architectural Practice of Nigeria

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Abstract:- Architecture arose from man's need and struggle for shelter, since then, his most formidable and persistent challenge has come from the climate he lives in. As far back as the renaissance epoch, architecture has been recognized as an intellectual discipline rather than merely a craft to be learned in apprenticeship. In Current contemporary Nigerian practice, where architectural craftsmen (draughtsman) and all shades of architecture illiterates become dominant parishioners of the same profession, charlatan has been responsible for many of the substandard buildings and known building failures. Charlatan has posed a severe danger to the building construction sector from the beginning of time. These issues do arise; however, they are not entirely distinct from various types of failures. More importantly, various attempts in the past, and even now, to checkmate or control the threats connected with charlatans in the construction sector have generated little or no results, and have frequently proven futile. However, the purpose of this article is to investigate the issue of charlatan in Nigerian architectural practice and the dangers associated with it, as well as to state the current role of the architect and other related professionals in the construction industry in order to find a long-term solution to the problem plaguing the industry.

Keywords:- *Apprentice, Architecture, Building Failure, Climate, Draughtsman, Charlatan, Shelter.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Building failure and collapse are not uncommon in the construction sector around the world. Its frequency of occurrence and the amount of related losses in terms of lives and property are especially prevalent in underdeveloped countries, despite the fact that occurrences are never planned. Collapsed constructions, such as bridges, buildings, or other sorts of engineered structures, are not unique to Nigeria. In fact, even a layperson on the streets of Nigeria will see the trend of buildings collapsing (Olabosipo and Adedamola, 2010).

According to Fadamiro, 2001, an informal survey conducted by the Nigeria Institute of Buildings (NIOB) revealed that during the past 66 years (1955-2021), more buildings may have collapsed during construction in Lagos state than in the rest of the country combined, with many similar cases across the country. Buildings are structures that provide shelter for people, their possessions, and their activities; they must be properly planned, designed, and built to achieve desired satisfaction from and conformity to the environment, using durable, stable, and yet aesthetically appealing materials to aid the user(s) comfort.

The inability of the component pieces to satisfy their expected requirements in part or whole, resulting in a collapse, is known as building failure. Building failures can occur at any time during the construction process or after it has been put into use. Bad design, faulty construction, use of sub-standard materials, hasty construction, foundation failure, lack of proper supervision, ineffective enforcement of the building codes by the relevant Planning Authorities, and lack of proper maintenance are all common causes of building collapse in Nigeria (Folagbade, 2001 and Badejo, 2009). When a component can no longer be depended on to perform its primary functions, it is said to have failed. Building failures can be of any of the following types:

- **Cosmetic failure:** This is a failure that occurs when an addition or subtraction is made on the building thus affecting the physical or structural outlook. Examples are deflections and visible cracks in slabs from loading, which is considered a defect but not a failure, although severe deflection can result in serious damage, which is now referred to as failure, it is considered a fault but not a failure.
- **Structural failure:** This is a failure that arises from faulty designs and material uses. It affects both the outlook as well as the stability of the building structure resulting into collapse of one or more parts of the structure.

Major catastrophic structural failures of buildings in Nigeria are predominantly due to man-made factors as asserted by Ayinuola and Olalusi, 2004; Dimuna, 2010; Amadi et al, 2012. However, considering the country's geographical location, there are relatively few occurrences where natural factors cause collapse, with the exception of a few incidents of erosion and flooding (Amadi et al, 2012), and these mainly affect low-rise (bungalow) buildings. Not merely to disparage the construction team and or experts involved in the fallen structures, but when someone is killed or gravely injured, these shortcomings become known to the public.

II. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

A. Aim

The aim of this project is to analyze and evaluate the different cases of building collapsed in Nigeria, the various factors that are responsible for the building collapsed and the best way to combat future occurrence.

B. Objectives

The objectives set out to achieve the above aim are to:

- explore the various building collapsed occurrence in Nigeria.
- analyze the factors that are responsible for the building collapsed.

- evaluate the effects of the building collapsed.
- recommend possible solutions to the building collapsed occurrence in Nigeria.

III. DEFINITION OF A CHARLATAN

A “Charlatan” is a person who pretends or falsely claims a professional skill and qualification they do not possess. Contextually (as it relates to the ARCON Registration Act No. 10 of the 1969); an individual that is not qualified to plan or assume complete responsibility for the design, construction or commissioning of architectural building process. In the architecture and construction sector, a charlatan is defined as a circumstance in which draftsmen or unregistered designers perform the duties of architects; participates in the design process, structural detailing, building servicing, cost analysis and construction of different kinds. Artisans and people in other fields also act as if they have skills they don't have. A mason may pose as an architect or a builder due to years of experience in the field, which invariably leads in building failures in a challenging situation requiring technical skill.

IV. HOW TO KNOW WHO A CHARLATAN IS IN ARCHITECTURE

A charlatanis when:

- Professionals such as Civil engineers, Project managers, Urban planners, Estate valuers and Surveyors, Quantity surveyors, Interior designers etc. add architectural services to their practice;
- A fully or partially trained architecture student /graduate with either ND, HND, B.Sc., MSc or Ph.D. degrees in Architecture unsupervised and without license or registration with the profession's statutory regulatory body (ARCON);
- Artisans and individuals who have acquired architectural and construction skills on site such as mason, carpenters, foremen, suppliers, contractors etc. practice architecture;
- Untrained individuals who have acquired knowledge and skill only in the use of architectural design software such as AutoCAD, Revit, etc. practice architecture; and
- Individuals who are licenced in a foreign country, but choose to operate in Nigeria can also be problematic due to insufficient knowledge of the local laws and practices, and /or licensed practice architecture in different country where they have no license. This issue may be overcome by obtaining local licencing, or working under the supervision of a practitioner licenced in Nigeria.

V. FACTORS AIDING CHARLATANIN ARCHITECTURE

A. Unemployment:

An unemployed graduate of the building/construction profession ravages the society in search for daily bread, charlatans may be raised as professionals in order to accomplish the work of other professions when the economic climate is better. Consequently, draftsmen and other charlatans thus look over the services to the large sector, producing “architecture” of the level of their competence.

Existing regulation stipulates that there is no building without a plan. The official answer to the pertinent question of who prepares the plan immediately according to ARCON reveals official confusion and lack of commitment to the ideals of architecture ‘The permission of draftsmen to design buildings not exceeding a floor’, thus, got grafted into the stork of designers without any requirement of a licensed architect's endorsement. This route consequently provides ample way for all other categories of charlatans into the design market. Other sharp practices like design duplications found in-road through the same route.

B. The Building Plan Approval Process:

The plan approval process of the country's Town Planning Authorities that is again devoid of professional architects' inputs further aggravates the already cankered situation as approval is given by professionals outside the discipline of architecture and who are not positioned to give proper architectural evaluation of architectural proposals.

C. Availability of Drafting Software:

In recent years, software such as AutoCAD, ArchiCAD, 3D Home Architects, Delux, Revit, and others that can enhance graphics, simulations, and drafting in the field of architecture have become an easy way and short cut for other allied professionals such as Civil Engineers, Mechanical Engineers, Electrical Engineers, Builders, and even untrained individuals or persons from other fields such as English, Geography, Mathematics, and so on to become full-time architects carrying laptops around and marketing their easy found way of enriching themselves to unsuspecting clients (public) who are defrauded of their money under the guise of receiving a professional service, and this is oftentimes substandard design that had never taken into consideration most of the design rudiments and minimum design requirements such as ventilation, lighting, circulation, functionality, and so on.

Charlatans has caused a lot of damages and blemish to the architectural profession, below are some of the shortcomings of charlatan in Nigeria.

The following are recent cases of collapsed buildings recorded around the country:

Date	Structure/Location	Causes of collapse	Casualties
June 2010	Residential under construction located at Oniru Estate, Victoria Island, Lagos.	Substandard materials, haphazard works.	1
June 2010	2-storey building under construction located at Nkwerre Street, Garki, Abuja.	Non-compliance with building regulations	1
July 2010	6 suspended floors for commercial purpose, located at Plot 702 Port-Harcourt crescent, Garki, Abuja.	Substandard materials and unqualified professionals	11
August 10, 2010	A wall fence, located at Aghaji crescent GRA, Enugu.	Drainage issues	1
August 11, 2010	Uncompleted 4-storey building located at Ikole street, Abuja.	Substandard materials & disregard for building regulations	23
September, 2010	4-storey building located at 28, Tinubu street, VI Lagos.	Structural defect/overloading	3
June 2011	Five-storey 11 Aderibigbe Street, located at Maryland, Lagos.	No geotechnical investigation,	None
June 2011	4-storey building located at Ndiagu Amechi Road, Enugu.	Undersized reinforcement,	3
June 13, 2012.	2-floor Commercial building located at Apo Mechanic Village,	There was no building permit and no qualified person on the job site.	14
July 2012	101-year-old 3-storey commercial building located at Hadeja Road by Ibrahim Taiwo Road, Gombe,	The structure has reached its maximum capacity.	1
August 8, 2012	2-storey building under construction 3, located at Ademola Awosike Road Kubwa Extension III, Abuja.	Poor quality materials, poor workmanship, inadequate/weak foundation.	3
November 20, 2012	Building in use located at Jakande estate Oke-Ake Afa, Isolo Lagos.	Structural failure and the government issued a safety notice, but the occupants ignored it.	3
November 3, 2013	A twin four-storey duplex located at Victoria Island, Lagos.	Unknown	4
September 12, 2014	Abu Naimi school building located at Bukuru Jos. September 2014.	Structural flaws and unauthorized conversion	10
12, 2014	Synagogue Church of All Nations (SCOAN) located at Ikotun-Egbe area of Lagos state, Nigeria.	Structural failure	116
12, 2014	Synagogue Warehouse Church, located at Lagos. Ikotun-Egbe area of Lagos state, Nigeria.	Demolition process	-
September 30, 2014	Liberty power bible church, Benin	Structural flaws and the use of inferior materials	-
March 13, 2015	4-storey building located at 6 Mogaji Street, Idumota, Lagos island	Unknown	1
July 15, 2015	3-storey building located at Ebuta meta Lagos.	Structural defects	-
October 21, 2015	3-storey building located at Swamp street Odunfa Lagos island.	Structural defects	-
March 9, 2016	A five-story building under construction located at Lekki, Lagos.	The authorized number of floors has been increased.	34
March 19, 2016	Two storey building located at Mile 12, Lagos.	Structural defects	1
April 2016.	Residential building located at Horizon 1, Lekki Garden, Ikate.	Structural defects	18
December 10, 2016	The Reigners Bible Church located at Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.	Structural failure	100
July 25, 2017	4-storey building located at 3, Massey St, Lagos Island, Lagos.	Undisclosed	6
July 8, 2017	A storey building located at Ulakwo junction, Owerri North LGA, Imo State.	Undisclosed	3
August 18, 2017	Four storey building located at Zulu Gambari Road, Ilorin.	Undisclosed	-
July 17, 2018	4-storey building located at Owelle Aja Layout, Obosi, Anambra.	Substandard materials with addition of two un-designed floors.	-
August 16,	4-storey building located at Jabi, FCT Abuja.	Substandard materials	2

2018			
October 18, 2018	3-storey building located at Okpuno, Otolo in Nnewi, Anambra.	Substandard materials.	-
October 2018	3-storey building located at Ifite Awka, Anambra State.	Substandard material	-
November 23, 2018	7-storey building located at Woji road, GRA phase 2, Port Harcourt.	Undisclosed	5
February 3, 2019	3-storey building located at Lagos Island.	Not reported	2
March 13, 2019	A three-storey building located at Ita Faaji area of Lagos state, Nigeria	The change of use of the building from the original purpose.	20
March 15, 2019	3-storey building under construction located at Sogoye, Bode area of Ibadan	During construction, the concrete was not properly cured.	-
August 17, 2018.	Collapse building in Jabi Area of Abuja	Undisclosed	-
November 18, 2018	Faculty of Social Sciences, located at Benue State University, Makurdi	Undisclosed	-
February 15, 2019.	Partial collapse of a seven-storey project of the proposed new library, University of Lagos, Lagos.	Undisclosed	-
	Three storey building located at No 14 Massey Street, Ita – Faji, Lagos Island, Lagos	Undisclosed	-
April 30, 2019	A-two storey building located at Eleyele Road in Jericho area Ibadan	Undisclosed	-
May 24, 2019	Four-storey building at Ezenwa Street by Oganloye Junction, Onitsha	Undisclosed	-
July 15, 2019	A-three-storey building at Seriki Street in Jos on Monday	Undisclosed	-
August 17, 2019	A wing of the popular Metro View Hotel close to Presco Campus of Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki.	Undisclosed	-
July 20, 2019	A-three-storey building under construction identified as the new 206 Hotel, located along Aghwana Avenue Abraka.	Undisclosed	-
November 1, 2021	The collapse of 21 storey building located at 44 B, C, D Gerrald Road, Ikoyi, Lagos.	Structural failure, Addition to the approved number of floors.	40
17 November, 2021.	The collapse of one storey building located at Sunny Filled, Flour Mills, Estate, Magbon, Badagry, Lagos.	Structural failure	5

Table 1: Collapsed buildings recorded in Nigeria between 2010 and 2021

Sources: Awoyera P. O., Alfa J., Odetoyan A., and Akinwumi I. I. (2021). *Building Collapse in Nigeria during recent years – Causes, effects and way forward.*

Bulletin of the Architects' Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON), 2019 Edition, Volume 07, 25 July 2019.

VI. CHARLATAN IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

Also, according to Olabosipo and Adedamola (2010), the following are the causes of building failures in Nigeria:

- 50 percent of the causes being owing to design flaws.
- 40 percent to faults on construction sites
- 10 percent as a result of poor design approval process for drawings and poor supervision at the construction stage.

Building failures can occur at any level of the design approval process, including the drawings stage and the supervision/construction stage. Almost every catastrophic incidence in Nigeria has been attributed to either developers who failed to follow building rules, or professional builders, architects, and engineers, as well as government institutions tasked with ensuring strict compliance. Other prominent

causes of building failures include overturning of structures due to high wind loads and slide of structures due to lateral loads.

Environmental changes, natural and man-made risks, poor presentation and interpretation in the design, and the deterioration of reinforced concrete which could occur as a result of: corrosion are all key causes of structural failures.

In addition, structural failures are caused by the inability of the design or supervision professional to conduct proper site investigations, accurately calculate design loads, avoid the use of sub-standard building materials, have a good design layout, and understand structural analysis and design principles.

Failure of a structure occurs when any portion of the structure, or the entire structure, becomes unsuited for the

intended loads for which it was designed. Any of the following three conditions could lead to a structure's failure:

- Serviceability limit state failure occurs when it becomes unserviceable by undergoing excessive deflection and cracking;
- Ultimate limit state failure happens when it fails by overturning, ultimate collapse, or wobbling of the columns. The structure is said to have failed in Ultimate limit state.
- Durability failure has to do with the weakening of the components beyond repairable limits.

The traditional materials used in previous centuries made buckling not a major structural problem and multi-storey structures were uncommon during these ages. There is a tendency to make sure important structures do not fail by using materials generously making many of the roman structures survived till date (Taiwo & Afolami, 2011). The standard of living has increased over the centuries bringing with it huge strides in technological advancements. Today, there are better procedures, more durable materials, better construction machinery and more advanced knowledge on construction. However, with all the advances in technology, there are still cases of collapse in countries of the world, though more prevalent in developing countries like Nigeria. Collapse in the developed countries is majorly due to natural causes or man-made causes like bombings like the world trade centre. However, collapse in developing countries are usually due to poor quality or substandard materials, poor supervision, non-adherence to standards and regulations, unqualified professional, overloading, no geotechnical/sub-soil investigation, poor construction procedure, illegal approval, wrong demolition process, lack of maintenance and numerous others (Ede, 2016).

- The possible causes of building collapse in Nigeria are:
 - The lack of a report on the soil load bearing test;
 - Quacks manage structural designs and technicalities;
 - There is a lack of coordination between professional organizations and the local planning authority;
 - Unqualified and inexperienced workers unable to comply to specifications;
 - Construction techniques that are poor or non-existent;
 - The use of low-quality construction materials;
 - There is a lack of competent monitoring;
 - Insufficient enforcement of current enabling building regulations;
 - Illegal conversions of structures, which frequently result in structural flaws;
 - Developers/landlords' flagrant disregard for town planning restrictions;
 - Some employees of the town planning authority have a compromised approach;
 - There are no penalties for errant professionals or landlords.

VII. STATUTORY REGULATING BODIES AND PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATIONS

They are in charge of overseeing and regulating the building's activities. They make sure that both the architect and the contractor follow all applicable laws, regulations, and constraints. They include; the town planner, building control officer and public health inspectors.

- Architects Registration council of Nigeria (ARCON)
- Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN)
- Quantity Surveyors Registration Council of Nigeria (QSRBN)
- Surveyors Registration Body of Nigeria (SURCON)
- Town Planners Registration Council of Nigeria (TOPREC)
- Council of Registered Builders in Nigeria (CORBON)
- Estate Surveyors and Valuers Registration Board of Nigeria (ESVARBON)

A. Architect:

Definition of Architecture in the context of ARCON act.

- Use of appellation "Architect": Subject to the provisions of the Act, a person shall not prepare or take full responsibility for the erection or commissioning of architectural building plans or practice or carry on business other than that having relevance to ship construction, or to landscape golf - links under any name, style or title containing the word "architect" unless he is a Nigerian citizen and registered with the Council.
- Definition : "The definition of architecture according to Architects Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON, 2001) is the art and science in theory and practice of design, erection, commissioning, maintenance and management and co-ordination of allied professional inputs thereto of buildings, or part thereof and the layout.

Initiates the design of the building project by translating the client's ideas into graphical and workable design/drawings. The Architectural profession is subject to an act of parliament i.e. a registered profession, with a regulatory body "ARCON". Only those qualified in accordance with the regulations can be admitted to the register. However, it is only the name 'architect' that is protected; anyone can carry out the role as long as the name is not used. As the name implies, the architect should be the master builder- the leader of the building industry or team.

An architect must visualize the interior as well as the exterior of the building, ensuring that the accommodation properly relates to the requirements of owner/user, within a predetermined set budget. Architects partner with other allied professionals to interpret with designs, and their involvement during the erection of a building, to achieve the ultimate success of his designs. The followings enumerate the role of architects as it evolves in present times:

- To advise and confer with the employer (not as a lawyer) on any restrictions that may apply to the usage of the site to be constructed on, such as restrictive covenants, adjoining owners' or the public's rights to the land, or

statutes and by-laws that impact the works to be completed.

- Examine the location, subsoil, and surrounding environment.
- To consult with the employer and provide advice on the proposed job.
- If required, prepare sketch plans and a specification for the proposed work, as well as an estimate of the likely cost.
- Detailed working drawings, construction details, and specification notes must be prepared.
- To confer with the employer and provide advice on possible tendering procedures.
- To provide the builder with copies of the contract drawings and specifications, to provide any additional drawings/details, to give instructions as needed, to supervise the work, to ensure that the contractor fulfils the contract, and to notify the employer if the contractor breaches the contract in any way.
- To perform his obligations to his employer as defined by the contract with his employer or the contract with the builder, and to act as the employer's agent in all matters relating to the work and the contract, except where the contract with the builder specifies otherwise, such as when he is required to act as arbitrator or quasi-arbitrator.

Architects must have a thorough understanding of construction and related trades, as well as a functional understanding of more specialized parts of construction, such as mechanical and electrical engineering services. Above all, they must be innovative and committed to resolving the difficulties identified in the brief.

B. Structural Engineer:

The Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria, COREN, was established by decree 55 of 1970 and amended by Decree 27 of 1992, now the "Engineers (Registration, etc.) Act, CAP E11 of 2004" Law of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

The Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria, COREN, is a body set-up by the Decrees 55/70 and 27/92 (now Acts 110). The Decrees gave the Council the authority to regulate and control engineering education and practice in Nigeria, as well as to ensure and enforce the registration of all engineering personnel (i.e. Engineers, Engineering Technologists, Engineering Technicians, and Engineering Craftsmen) and consulting firms wishing to practice or engage in engineering.

They will create structural designs from the foundations to the roof, as well as provide guidance on ground conditions on projects that require such services. They will be responsible for the building's structural stability, which includes:

- Structural advices.
- Structural details and specification.
- Structural design and oversight of ongoing construction.

They should be available throughout the design stages as an early appointment and their advice will greatly influence the outcome of the project, which in many cases cannot be furthered without the basic structural information

being available. Some structural engineers will offer drainage and other infrastructure advice; alternatively, design input on these issues may be provided by an engineer specializing solely in this type of work.

C. Service Engineer:

These are services that deal with the mechanical and electrical aspects of a construction project. Services engineers provides advice, specification and schematic or detailed drawings and are sometimes responsible for obtaining tenders from specialist firms. They should be available throughout the early stages of design and should be actively involved in ensuring that services are properly integrated into the design.

D. Quantity Surveyor:

Quantity Surveyors Registration Board of Nigeria (QSRBN) is the regulatory body of the quantity surveying profession and practice in Nigeria. It was established by Decree No. 31 of December 5, 1986, now CAP 383 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN). To ensure that all quantity surveying graduates produced by higher institutions of learning in Nigeria meet internationally required standards.

He is the project accountant, employed solely to control the project cost through; preliminary cost advice, preparation of bills of quantities, conduct valuations and other related cost expertise for the building project. Their involvement was limited to a small but crucial element of the development process. This responsibility was quickly expanded to include preparing interim certificate valuations and negotiating final accounts with the contractor. In today's world, a quantity surveyor's job can be summarized as follows:

- Preliminary cost advice.
- Cost planning.
- Value management.
- Risk analysis.
- Procurement and tendering procedures.
- Contract documentation.
- Tender evaluation.
- Cash flow forecasting, financial reporting and interim payments.
- Final accounting.
- Insolvency services
- Technical auditing.

E. Land Surveyor:

The surveyors Council of Nigeria (SURCON) was established by decree on 14th. December 1989, of Decree 44 Known as the surveyors Registration Council of Nigeria.

F. Its mandate is to:

- Securing, in accordance with the provisions of this Act, the establishment and maintenance of a register of persons entitled to practice the profession and the publication, from time to time, of lists of such persons;
- Regulating and controlling the practice of the profession in all its ramifications;

This is a specialist that measures land area and height levels of the site in relation to the town and country at large.

He gives the total dimensions of the land and uses denoted beacons to mark necessary points and stations. He also assists in the proper location of the building and other services on site.

G. Town Planners:

Town planners' registration Council of Nigeria (TOPREC) was established by decree no 3 of 1988 to regulate the practice of Town planning in Nigeria. Its mandate includes the followings

- ensuring the development and maintenance of a registry of persons authorized to practice the profession in conformity with this Act, as well as the dissemination of names of those persons from time to time;
- regulating and controlling the practice of the profession in all its aspects and ramifications

H. Builder:

The Council of Registered Builders of Nigeria, CORBON was established by Federal Republic of Nigeria Act Cap No. 40(formerly known as Decree No. 45 of 1989), and now established by BUILDERS REGISTRATION ACT CAP. B13LFN 2004.

The Council, as defined in Section 2 of the law, is a body corporate empowered to regulate the practice of building construction, maintenance, and management in Nigeria.

The contractor employs him to plan, monitor, and supervise the project's progress through site administration, project construction management, project monitoring, and assessment. Depending on the scale and complexity of the contract, he can work as contract manager, site agent, or supervisor.

I. Building Contractor:

This is a person or company that carries out the construction work as specified in the blueprints. He assembles a team of all relevant professionals, supervises construction, and guarantees that all necessary steps are completed to complete a project. A building contractor is a company that works on the design, development, and construction of a building.

J. Estate surveyors:

The Estate Surveyors and Valuers Registration Board of Nigeria was established by Decree No. 24 of 1975 now CAP E13 LFN 2007 to regulate the practice of Estate surveyors in Nigeria.

Source:NIA/ARCON ACPE Preparatory Seminar-16th. July 2019.

K. Recommendations

With all that has been mentioned in this study article, the following advice will suffice if followed and implemented, and the practice of charlatan will be decreased or eliminated. Governments and agencies should guarantee that all processes and construction procedures are followed in order to achieve effective stage management and certification for compliance with development rules and regulations. All professional organisations or institutes, as well as their

regulatory bodies, should guarantee that their members follow the processes involved in service provision and delivery, with harsh penalties for those who do not. To aid in the fight against charlatans and protect standards, the public should always patronize professionals for their development needs in the building construction sector. The government, agencies, and professional organizations should guarantee that the public is constantly informed about their operations in the fight against charlatans and the accompanying threat. All project designs and drawings should have on it ARCON Project Registration Number (APRN) before approval and implementation. The APRN was initiated by ARCON to curb charlatan.

VIII. CONCLUSION

It is no longer an exaggeration to argue that the charlatan epidemic has harmed the development of the Nigerian construction industry. The failures linked with charlatan are immense and difficult to quantify. The environmental damage, as well as the shame it brings to the industry's specialists, should not be neglected. The resulting loss of life and assets linked with building collapse in the face of the current unfavorable climate is cause for concern for everyone (Dare, 2001). Indeed, victims are not limited to the residents of collapsed buildings, let alone passers-by or neighbors and their properties, which are sometimes packed up into the vortex of the phenomena. While many other industrialized countries, such as Malaysia, Singapore, and Arab countries, build skyscrapers (even in locations prone to natural disasters such as earthquakes), we still have incidences of building collapse involving two or three-story structures in Nigeria. It is acknowledged, however, that charlatans are responsible for more than half of all building collapses and other related failures; therefore, if professionals and all stakeholders are allowed or forced to perform their full responsibilities to society in relation to the current trend of development in the industry, the threat will be eliminated. During the design and construction process, certified professionals must conduct thorough evaluations and checks. Finally, investors and building owners should be educated about the risk of a building collapsing due to excessive intervention in the construction process.

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